

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 57

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 57

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 57:0 For the choir director; <i>set to</i> †Al-tashheth. A °Mikhtam of David, ^when he fled from Saul in the cave.</p>	<p>Psa. 57:1 לְמִנְצֵחַ אֶל־תְּשַׁחַת לְדָוִד מִכְתָּם בְּבִרְחוֹ מִפְּנֵי־שָׂאוּל</p>
<p>Psa. 57:1 Be gracious to me, O God, be gracious to me, For my soul ^atakes refuge in You; And in the ^bshadow of Your wings I will take refuge Until destruction ^cpasses by. ² I will cry to God Most High, To God who ^aaccomplishes <i>all things</i> for me. ³ He will ^asend from heaven and save me; He reproaches him who ^btramples upon me. ²Selah. God will send forth His ^alovingkindness and His ³truth.</p>	<p>בְּרַחֲמֶיךָ : ² תִּנְנֵנִי אֱלֹהִים אֲנִי כִי בְךָ חָסִיחַ נַפְשִׁי וּבְצֵל־כַּנְפֶיךָ אֶחְסֶה עַד יַעֲבֹר הַיּוֹת : ³ אֶקְרָא לְאֱלֹהִים עֲלִיּוֹן לֹאֵל גִּמְרַע עָלַי : ⁴ יִשְׁלַח מִשָּׁמַיִם וַיּוֹשִׁיעַנִי חַתָּךְ שְׂאֵפֵי סֶלָה יִשְׁלַח אֱלֹהִים חֲסִדּוֹ וַאֲמַתּוֹ : ⁵ נַפְשִׁי אִבְתּוֹךָ לְבָאֵם אֲשַׁכְּבָה לְהַטִּים בְּנֵי־אָדָם שְׁנִיחָם חַנּוּת וְחַצִּים וְלִשְׁוֹנָם תִּרְבַּח חַדָּה : ⁶ רִוְמָה עַל־הַשָּׁמַיִם אֱלֹהִים עַל כָּל־הָאָרֶץ כְּבוֹדֶךָ : ⁷ רַחֲמֵיךָ אֲהַכִּינוּ לְבַעֲמֵי כַּפְּךָ נַפְשִׁי כָרוּ לְפָנַי שִׁיחָה נָפְלוּ בַתּוֹכָה סֶלָה : ⁸ נִכּוֹן לִבִּי אֱלֹהִים נִכּוֹן לִבִּי אֲשִׁירָה וְאֶזְמָרָה : ⁹ עֲוֹרָה כְּבוֹדִי עֲוֹרָה הַנִּבְּל וְכַנּוֹר אֶעֱרָה שָׁחַר : ¹⁰ אֲוֹרָה בְּעַמִּים אֲדַנִּי אֶזְמָרְךָ בְּל־אֲמִים : ¹¹ כִּי־גִדְּלָה עַד־שָׁמַיִם חֲסִדֶּךָ וְעַד־שְׁחַקִּים אֲמַתּוֹךָ : ¹² רִוְמָה עַל־שָׁמַיִם אֱלֹהִים עַל כָּל־הָאָרֶץ כְּבוֹדֶךָ :</p>
<p>Psa. 57:4 My soul is among ^alions; I must lie among those who breathe forth fire, <i>Even</i> the sons of men, whose ^bteeth are spears and arrows And their ^ctongue a sharp sword. ⁵ ^aBe exalted above the heavens, O God; <i>Let</i> Your glory <i>be</i> above all the earth. ⁶ They have ¹prepared a ^anet for my steps; My soul is ^bbowed down; They ^cdug a pit before me; They <i>themselves</i> have ^dfallen into the midst of it. Selah.</p>	<p>הַנִּבְּל וְכַנּוֹר אֶעֱרָה שָׁחַר : ¹⁰ אֲוֹרָה בְּעַמִּים אֲדַנִּי אֶזְמָרְךָ בְּל־אֲמִים : ¹¹ כִּי־גִדְּלָה עַד־שָׁמַיִם חֲסִדֶּךָ וְעַד־שְׁחַקִּים אֲמַתּוֹךָ : ¹² רִוְמָה עַל־שָׁמַיִם אֱלֹהִים עַל כָּל־הָאָרֶץ כְּבוֹדֶךָ :</p>

Psa. 57:7 *“My ^hheart is steadfast, O God, my heart is steadfast;*

I will sing, yes, I will sing praises!

⁸ *Awake, ^amy glory!*

Awake, ^hharp and lyre!

I will awaken the dawn.

⁹ *“I will give thanks to You, O Lord, among the peoples;*

I will sing praises to You among the ¹nations.

¹⁰ *For Your ^alovingkindness is great to the heavens*

And Your ¹truth to the clouds.

¹¹ *“Be exalted above the heavens, O God;*

*Let Your glory *be* above all the earth.*

References

Psalm 57:0

Lit *Do Not Destroy*

¹Possibly, *Epigrammatic Poem* or *Atonement Psalm*

¹1 Sam 22:1; 24:3

Psalm 57:1

^aPs 2:12; 34:22

^bRuth 2:12; Ps 17:8; 36:7; 63:7; 91:4

^cIs 26:20

Psalm 57:2

^aPs 138:8

Psalm 57:3

¹Or *snaps at*

²*Selah* may mean: *Pause, Crescendo* or *Musical interlude*

³Or *faithfulness*

^aPs 18:16; 144:5, 7

^bPs 56:2

^cPs 25:10; 40:11

Psalm 57:4

^aPs 35:17; 58:6

^bProv 30:14

^cPs 55:21; 59:7; 64:3; Prov 12:18

Psalm 57:5

^aPs 57:11; 108:5

Psalm 57:6

¹Or *spread*

^aPs 10:9; 31:4; 35:7; 140:5

^bPs 145:14

^cPs 7:15

^dProv 26:27; 28:10; Eccl 10:8

Psalm 57:7

^aPs 57:7-11; 108:1-5

^bPs 112:7

Psalm 57:8

^aPs 16:9; 30:12

^bPs 150:3

Psalm 57:9

¹Lit *peoples*

^aPs 108:3

Psalm 57:10

¹Or *faithfulness*

^aPs 36:5; 103:11; 108:4

Psalm 57:11

^aPs 57:5; 108:5

Targum

Psa. 57:1 For praise, concerning the distress at the time when David said, “Do not harm.” It was spoken by David, humble and innocent, when he fled from Saul’s presence in the cave. ² Have mercy on me, O God, have mercy on me, for in your word my soul has trusted, and in the shade of your Presence I will be confident until the turmoil passes. ³ I will pray before God Most High, the mighty one, who commanded the spider who completed a web for me. ⁴ He will send his angel from heaven above, and he will redeem me; he has put to shame the one who bruises me, forever; God will send his goodness and his truth. ⁵ My soul glows while in the midst of flames; I will sleep among coals that burn, the sons of men whose teeth are like lances and arrows, and whose tongue is like a sharp sword. ⁶ Be exalted over the angels of heaven, O God; your glory is over all those who dwell on earth. ⁷ They have set a net for my footsteps; my soul is bowed down; they dug before me a pit, they have fallen into the middle of it forever. ⁸ My heart is turned to your Torah, O LORD; my heart is turned to fear you; I will praise and sing! ⁹ Wake up, my glory! Wake up to praise by means of the harp and lyre; wake up for the prayer of morning. ¹⁰ I will give thanks before you among the peoples, O LORD; I will praise you among the nations. ¹¹ For your goodness is high to reach the heavens, and your truth, to the clouds. ¹² Be exalted, O LORD, above the angels of heaven; O God, above all the inhabitants of the earth is your glory.

Spiritual Awareness

The spiritual rewrite for the verses is in bold.

Introduction

King Saul and three thousand of his soldiers were chasing David through the wilderness of En-Gedi. Saul walked into a cave where David and his men were hiding. While Saul was relieving himself, David's men wanted to kill him. Instead, David decided to cut off a piece of Saul's cloak, thus proving David's loyalty to Saul. David hoped that Saul would stop pursuing him in order to kill him.

אלֹ־תִשְׁחַת (al – tash'chat) means “not destroy.” This phrase is found in the superscript of Psalms 57, 58, 59, and 75. All four psalms deal with conditions of potential general ruin and corruption unless the LORD would intervene and put a stop to it.

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory. Let not destruction come. A psalm by David when he fled from Saul in the cave.

Verse one

David was placed under a tremendous test of moral and spiritual fortitude. He needed a divine factor to make the godly choice.

**Endow my spirit O God, endow my spirit, for in You my soul puts its trust.
And I shall trustingly hide myself in the shadow of Your wings until that
which is now being shaped shall have passed.**

Verse two

Even though the LORD seems far away from David, he calls upon Him for help.

I will call upon God, the Most High, to the Almighty one who decrees my fate.

Verse three

Saul and his men were chasing an innocent David. Since they wanted to kill him and he was the anointed one of the LORD, these men were blasphemers.

He will send from heaven and save me; He reproaches him who tramples upon me. Meditate on this verse. God will send forth His lovingkindness and His truth.

Verse four

David uses the metaphor of the lion to refer to the men pursuing him. When a lion kills, it is not concerned about the animal it kills. To lie down with the lions means that David was confident that Saul's men would not kill him because the LORD was protecting him.

As for me, amidst lions, I lie down peacefully beside those aflame with rage, sons of man whose teeth are spears and arrows and whose tongue is a sharp sword.

Verse five

Even though the LORD is in the Heavens, His glory is felt and seen upon the earth.

Yet even though You are high above the heavens, Your glory is upon the earth.

Verse six

David says that Saul's men had tried to kill him before. However, the LORD helped David.

They have prepared a net for my steps; My soul is bowed down; They dug a pit before me; They have fallen into the midst of it. Meditate on this verse.

Verse seven

David's enemies had hoped to change David's heart. However, they succeeded in strengthening David's reliance on the LORD. The repetition is for emphasis.

My heart was made steadfast, O God, my heart was made steadfast, so that I uttered hymns and sang songs.

Verse eight

The individual must do spiritual growth and awakening. Repetition is used for emphasis.

Awake, O my honor, awake, O psaltery and harp; I shall awaken the dawn.

Verse nine

David was in flight, persecuted, and hiding in a dark cave. Things looked bad for David. However, he praised the LORD.

I will acknowledge You among the peoples, my Master, I will sing praises unto You among the nations.

Verse ten

The Sefirah Chesed is great in Heaven and Your faithfulness unto the clouds.

Verse Eleven

Yet even though You are High above heavens, Your glory is upon all the earth.

Complete Psalm Rewrite Emphasizing Spiritual Awareness

To the Sefirah Netzach who grants victory. Let not destruction come. A psalm by David when he fled from Saul in the cave.

Endow my spirit O God, endow my spirit, for in You my soul puts its trust. And I shall trustingly hide myself in the shadow of Your wings until that which is now being shaped shall have passed.

I will call upon God, the Most High, to the Almighty one who decrees my fate. He will send from heaven and save me; He reproaches him who tramples upon me. Meditate on this verse. God will send forth His lovingkindness and His truth.

As for me, amidst lions, I lie down peacefully beside those aflame with rage, sons of man whose teeth are spears and arrows and whose tongue is a sharp sword.

Yet even though You are high above the heavens, Your glory is upon the earth. They have prepared a net for my steps; My soul is bowed down; They dug a pit before me; They have fallen into the midst of it. Meditate on this verse.

My heart was made steadfast, O God, my heart was made steadfast, so that I uttered hymns and sang songs.

Awake, O my honor, awake, O psaltery and harp; I shall awaken the dawn.

I will acknowledge You among the peoples, my Master, I will sing praises unto You among the nations.

The Sefirah Chesed is great in Heaven and Your faithfulness unto the clouds.

Yet even though You are High above heavens, Your glory is upon all the earth.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

MHK V5 1/17/2016

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

MHK V1.1 6/23/14

